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Aspirations, Expectations, Family Support and Academic Achievement of Grade 11 Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the levels of aspirations, expectations, family support and academic achievements of grade 11 students of Congressman Ramon A. Arnaldo High School, Bgry. Banica, Roxas City, Capiz. Respondents of the study were 152 grade 11 students who were officially enrolled at Congressman Ramon A. Arnaldo High School, Bgry. Banica, Roxas City, Capiz, during the School Year 2018-2019. The Following are the significant findings: (1) The level of aspirations from the respondents is “very high”; (2) the level of expectations from the respondents is “very high”; (3) the level of family support from the respondents is “high”; (4) the level of academic achievement from the respondents is “very satisfactory”; (5) There is a significant relationship between the following variables: academic achievement and aspiration; academic achievement and expectation; and, aspiration and expectation. However, there is no significant relationship between the following variables: academic achievement and family support; family support and aspiration; and, family support and expectation.

Keywords: *aspirations, expectations, family support and academic achievements*

Introduction

A number of researchers in the past have addressed the causal relationship between aspirations and school achievement. It is not possible to foresee school achievement on the grounds of aspirations or vice versa. Numerous students from diverse ethnic, racial and socio-economic backgrounds are likely to develop high educational and occupational aspirations that are irrelevant to their present or future school performance (Khattab, 2015).

Since aspirations, on the one hand, at least as have been defined in these studies, reflect hopes and dreams, they are likely to be disengaged from the socio-economic and school reality of students. Expectations, on the other hand, are more likely to be associated with the socio-economic circumstances, and as such a much better predictor for school accomplishment (Beal & Crockett, 2010)

Past studies on aspirations and school achievement have basically focused on the question whether or not aspirations can be utilized as a vehicle to raise school achievement (Khattab, 2015). The conclusion of most of these studies is that the evidence to connect raising aspirations with improving school achievement is either exceptionally slim or profoundly flawed. A few of these studies have pointed out that some students tend to hold high aspirations even beyond what the labor market can support (Khattab, 2015), which has driven the researchers to address the assumption among policy makers that raising aspirations will enhance educational achievement (Gorard et al., 2012). However, not a few studies can explain how aspirations affect on future educational behavior in conjunction with different levels of expectations and current (or future) school performance. This study aims to analyze the impact of the entire extent of aligned and misaligned aspirations on students' future educational behavior.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of the study was to determine the relationship of student’s aspirations, expectations and family support to the academic achievements of Grade 11 students. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of aspirations, of Grade 11 students at Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School?
2. What is the level of expectations of Grade 11 students at Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School?
3. What is the level of family support of Grade 11 students at Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School?
4. What is the level of academic achievement of Grade 11 students at Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School?
5. Are there significant relationships among the aspirations, expectations family support, and achievement of Grade 11 students at Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School

Literature Review

Adolescents’ academic aspirations in particular have been found to be influential to their future educational and occupational success (Beal & Crockett, 2010). The parent–child relationship gives a transmission of the family cultural values and standards to children that is both positive and smooth. It shapes the child’s aspirations, career choices and their propensity to pursue additional education (Watts & Bridges, 2006).

Children do not need to stay as poor as their parents. Poor parents did not want their children to be like them. They wanted their children to have a job. Aspirations are also motivators to change their current state of life, instead of remaining immersed in it. Despite living in poverty, parents were trying their best to bring success to their children’s education (Tafere, 2014).

Expectations refer to what people think will happen, aspirations refer to what they hope will happen (Jacob and Wilder, 2010).

Educational expectations and aspirations not only are strong predictors of educational attainment but also reflect self-perceptions and influence attitudes toward school that, if unfulfilled, result in frustration (Krahn and Taylor 2005).

Ryan and Deci (2000) states that educational performances and expectations may be influenced by micro-interactions among peers. "Peers effect on educational motivation, engagement and achievement through information exchange, modeling and support of peer's standards and values".

Moreover, Munro (2011) in her review of the UK child protection system, emphasizes that support for families is vital in promoting children's well-being. The academic performance of students depends upon the parental inclusion in their scholastic activities to achieve the higher level of quality in scholastic success (Barnard, 2004). All forms of partial involvement strategies appear to be valuable. However, those that offer more types of roles for the parents to play, and occur over an extended period of time appear to be more effective (Becher, 1984).

Furthermore, the study of Pinantoan (2013) pointed out the influence of parental involvement on a student's academic success should not be underestimated. The significance of support system that a student gets from home is similarly vital as his brain power, work morals and genetics which all work in the accomplishment of his goal in life.

Feyfant and Rey's (2006) argue that there are families who have the right intentions but are powerless especially those from rural backgrounds or those with little in the way of education. However, being wealthy may be one thing and financing schools or providing scholastic materials to pupils may be another. The study sought to discover whether parents irrespective of their socio-economic status give school funds educational materials and other requirements for the good of scholastic enhancement and the extent to which availability of these materials improves pupils' academic performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The survey-correlational method of research was utilized in this study. In this research method, the survey-correlational was used for the quantitative design using the questionnaires.

The data in this study were collected using the researcher-made questionnaire instrument for family support, a standardized questionnaire developed by Barreda (1998) measured student aspirations and the Academic Expectation Scale Questionnaire developed by Vallerand (1992) was also used to measure students' expectations. The descriptive statistics used were frequency count, mean, and standard deviation; and the inferential statistics used was Pearson r. The level of significance was set at 0.05 alpha level.

Respondents

The participants of this study were the one hundred fifty-two (152) grade 11 students of Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School located at Banica, Roxas City for the school year 2018-2019.

The participants were selected using the lottery technique. This means that all the names of the Grade 11 students in Cong. Ramon A. Arnaldo High School located at Banica, Roxas City were written in rolled slips of paper and were placed in a box. The required number of participants per section were determined using the formula of Slovin (David, 2002).

Instrument

To obtain the quantitative data, the researcher utilized a questionnaire composed of four parts. Part 1 gathered the demographic profile of the participants of the study; Part 2, the Student Aspirations Scale was used to determine the level of aspirations of the respondents. This is a 14-item questionnaire which was adopted by the researcher from Barreda (1998); Part 3, the Academic Expectations Questionnaire was used to obtain data on their academic expectations. This 18-item standardized questionnaire was adopted from Vallerand (1992); Part 4, the Family Support Questionnaire, was used to gather data on the level of family support given by their respective families to the respondents. This is a researcher-made questionnaire composed of 40 items. It was subdivided into 4 components which measure the following areas of parental support (Financial-10 items, Emotional-10 Items, Academic-10 items, Socio-psychological-10 items).

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was solicited first from the principal of the target school. Upon approval, the researcher personally distributed the research instruments to the participants. When all the instruments were answered and retrieved, they were tallied, tabulated, computer-processed, analyzed and interpreted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences Software (SPSS). The results were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Ethical Considerations

To address various concerns in preserving the privacy and security of the respondents, the researcher followed integrity and supported the Data Privacy Law and kept their identities and information discreet.

The researcher presented and discussed the informed consent and assent to the respondents before the conduct of the study to give them the freedom to decline their participation (see Appendix B & C. To assure them of their privacy, the researcher followed these steps: (1) distinguishing and coding of data; (2) no particular identifying information or mark in the survey questionnaire or the computer; (3) a secure storage for the data throughout the study; (4) destroying of information after use.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Aspiration of Grade 11 Students

Table 1 shows the level of aspirations of the respondents. The result reveals that the level of aspirations of grade 11 students is “very high” ($M=4.29$, $SD=.51$)

Table 1. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Aspiration*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>SD</i>
Aspiration	4.29	Very High	.51

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

Table 1 shows that the respondents generally had a “very high” level of aspiration. This shows that student’s aspiration may be influenced by their economic conditions. Most of the respondents come from low-level to middle-level family income earners. Poverty for them is not a hindrance towards success. This becomes their motivation to go on with their studies, have a bachelor’s degree, and find a work so they could support their selves and also their family.

The result of the study conforms with study of Tafere (2014) that children do not want to remain as poor as their parents. Poor parents did not want their children to be like them. They wanted their children to have a job. Aspirations are also motivators to change their current state of life, instead of remaining immersed in it. Despite living in poverty, parents were trying their best to bring success to their children’s education.

The Level of Expectations of Grade 11 Students

Table 2 showed that the respondents had generally “very high” expectation with a grand mean of 4.36. The result revealed that respondents would pursue their college education and find a decent job and have "the good life" in the future which includes having a better salary.

Table 2. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Expectation*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>SD</i>
Expectation	4.36	Very High	.51

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

Moreover, the result showed that respondents felt that much concentration is needed to focus on the subject they were studying, for them to really absorb the concepts and techniques. Students give emphasis on the accuracy of their work and they are interested as well in finishing it thoroughly.

This was supported by the study of Ryan and Deci (2000) stating that educational performances and expectations may be influenced by micro-interactions among peers. “Peers effect on educational motivation, engagement and achievement through information exchange, modeling and support of peer’s standards and values”.

Family Support of Grade 11 Students

Table 3 shows the level of family support. The result reveals that the level of family support of grade 11 students is “high” ($M=3.93$, $SD=.53$).

Table 3. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Family Support*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>SD</i>
Family Support	3.93	High	.53

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

The findings of the present study revealed that the level of family support in the education of grade 11 students was high. It implies that the parents in the present study enjoyed power and are overly active participants in their child’s education whether financially, emotionally, academically, or psycho-socially.

This confirms with the study of Becher (1984) that all forms of partial involvement strategies seem to be useful. Be that as it may, those that offer more sorts of roles for the parents to play and happen over an expanded period of time appear to be more successful.

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students

Table 4 shows the level of Academic Performance. The result reveals that the level of Academic Performance of grade 11 students is “high” ($M=4.29$, $SD=.51$) As displayed in the table, majority of the respondents belong to the grade range of 85 to 89. The results could

be attributed to the strict retention policy of the program of DepEd that requires an average of 75 or higher to be able to proceed to the next level.

Table 4. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Achievement*

Variable	Mean	Description	SD
Academic Achievement	87.80	Very Satisfactory	.51

Legend: 90-100, Outstanding; 85-89, Very Satisfactory; 80-84, Satisfactory; 75-79, Fairly Satisfactory; < 75, Did Not Meet Expectations

Moreover, parents are one of the factors affecting the academic performance of their children. Their characteristics in terms of education and income somehow may affect student's academic outcome.

This conforms to Feyfant and Rey's (2006) contention that there are families who have the proper intentions but are powerless particularly those from rural backgrounds or those with little in the way of education. However, being wealthy may be one thing and financing schools or providing scholastic materials to pupils may be another. The study sought to discover whether parents irrespective of their socio-economic status give school funds educational materials and other requirements for the good of scholastic enhancement and the extent to which availability of these materials improves pupils' academic performance.

Relationships among Aspirations, Expectations, Family Support, and Achievement of Students

Table 5 shows the relationships among aspirations, expectations, family support and achievement of students. The results of Pearson r reveals that there are no significant relationships among academic achievement and family support ($r=.128$, $p=.116$); family support and aspirations ($r=.070$, $p=.393$); and, family support and expectations ($r=.021$, $p=.801$). Conversely, the result shows that there is a significant relationship between academic achievement and aspirations ($r=.172$, $p=.034$); academic achievement and expectations ($r=.267$, $p=.001$); and aspirations and expectations ($r=.776$, $p=.000$).

Table 4. *Pearson r Among Academic Achievement, Family Support, Aspiration and Expectation*

Variables	R	Sig
Academic Achievement and Family Support	.128	.116
Academic Achievement and Aspiration	.172*	.034
Academic Achievement and Expectation	.267*	.001
Family support and Aspiration	.070	.393
Family support and Expectation	.021	.801
Aspiration and Expectation	.776*	.000

* $p < 0.05$ significant @ 5% alpha level

The result shows that academic achievement has no significant relationship to family support because family income and other forms of support may not directly improve academic performance. Better achieving students tend to perform academically in the absence of family support. Money or other forms of family support does not hinder the student to study harder to achieve a higher grade. It may imply that student's self-concept and motivation may be among the other factors that influence her/his academic achievement.

Academic achievement has a significant relationship to aspiration because their high aspirations in life, coincides with their capability in which they find it easier to achieve higher performance in the school. It may imply that there are possibilities that the academic achievement influencing students' aspirations may be due to family, school and personal factors including financial support, academic, emotional and psycho-social support from their family. It is difficult to separate a student's academic performance and achievement from her/his academic aspirations as the aspirations serve as motivation for achievement.

Achievement has a significant relationship to expectations. It is likely that high parental expectations work through a number of mechanisms such as strengthening or improvement of self-efficacy among students, well defined targets and life goals. It may imply that impact of parental expectations affect the future educational behavior of students in different ways and at different levels.

On the other hand, family support has no significant relationship to aspiration because different classes emphasize different values, possess different levels of resources and human capital and have different parenting styles. Hence, it is not usually sufficient to have a great parent-child relationship in order to raise students' aspirations. In order for parents to maintain and help fulfil their child's high aspirations, they must provide them with the desired resources and skills. Disadvantaged parents (e.g. working class) do not continuously have the information or resources to help their children convert the high aspirations into actions and future accomplishment. This suggests as it were that in more financially well-off families, family social capital and relationships play a vital part in enabling students to benefit from family human, financial and social capital.

Family support has no significant relationship to expectations because parents with limited education and fewer economic resources tend to feel less efficacious helping their children with school work than do more advantaged parents, additionally feel less comfortable interacting with teachers and other education professionals. These parents may create low scholastic expectations for their children even when the children's previous school performance is generally high in the event that they worry that they will not be able to provide support within the future due to a need of mental, cultural or material resources. On the other hand, when parents believe that they are

capable of helping their children succeed at school, they may hold high expectations concerning their scholastic performance.

Lastly, the result showing that aspirations have significant relationship to expectations may imply that students are bound to perform well in school, now and in the future. It also implies that the student should note their educational aspirations regardless of any constraints (e.g., finances, grades, etc.) that will keep them from accomplishing this level of achievement. The expectations question on the other hand inquires students to note the level of schooling that they realistically expect to complete, showing that the students should factor into their response the potential constraints which will prevent their educational achievement.

Conclusions

The “very high” level in terms of aspirations of the grade 11 students point out that the students have high hopes of becoming successful in the future. This could be implicated that the Senior High School program is viewed as a stepping stone for them to achieve the desires that they want to attain. Hence, despite the difficulty posed by the different subjects in the grade 11, they still have favorable attitude towards it. The favorable demeanor can also be credited to the approach they utilized in studying their subjects.

The “very high” level in terms of expectations of the grade 11 students showed that that the vast majority of them not only aspire to attend college after high school, but see college as a realistic goal as well. Parents indicated that they are all communicating their educational expectations in some way to their child. However, far too many parents, in particular those with less education and low-achieving students, indicated that they do not have the knowledge regarding what it will take for their child to be eligible for college, as well as the options available to finance a college education. The reality remains that of the 70% of high school seniors who continue on to college after high school, 30% drop out after their first year. More needs to be done in order to help students and their parents make this clear dream a reality.

The “high” level in terms of family support of the grade 11 students showed that parents were actively involved in promoting their children’s learning, providing them security, good foundation skills and positive self-concept. They give supportive reactions and bolster the educational aspirations of their children. Parents are willing to contribute their knowledge and abilities to enhance the learning experiences of their students. It can be said that parents' inclusion within the academic performance of students emerges from parents' eagerness and positive parenting style. These in return are seen by the students, and at best internalized by them hence, resulting to high achievement in academic activities.

The “very satisfactory” level in terms of academic achievement of grade 11 students showed that the achievement of grade 11 students is generally dependent on persistence in working towards that goal, specifically through studying hard, coupled with positive attitude and behavior towards senior high school years and later on going to college. The positive attitude of students paired with effective study habits might lead to higher academic performance and therefore higher chance of passing the different subjects and proceed to the next level. To be able to graduate in the senior high school, for some finding work after they graduate, and for others who will proceed to college, and later on finding a suitable work, there is a need for the students to have a passion for the field they are entering into because no matter how effective the other factors would be, at the end of the day, what will make them truly fruitful is their love for the field that will make them overcome all difficulties that they may face.

The significant relationships among student’s level in aspiration and expectation, and academic achievement indicates that students who believe that effort is the key determinant of academic success are not likely to base their desires on past performance since effort is generally controllable and consequently less stable over time. In contrast, those students who believe that performance is a function of his/her own ability, which is frequently perceived as relatively stable over time, are more likely to see past accomplishment as a reliable indicator of future performance. To the extent that students are likely to focus on the role of effort in achievement, the effects of past performance are likely to be less salient for them in anticipating future performance than for other groups.

However, there is no significant relationship among student’s level of academic achievement, family support, aspiration, and expectation indicates that student’s belief about their academic competence may not be as strongly determinative of achievement as for other students. As we noted, more studies examining students' competency beliefs are necessary in order to compare the importance of this belief as a mediator between parental expectations and student outcomes. Regarding the association between parental expectations and their involvement in schooling, it suggests that for students, higher parental expectations did not necessarily translate into the type of parental involvement that is directly related to academic achievement.

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